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Investigation of Iran's high-speed Railway, Specifications, and Brief analysis of Rail-based Accidents

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Abstract.

The world depends heavily on automobiles nowadays. The majority of people in the globe now use cars for their daily activities, and their use of these vehicles has significantly expanded. Traffic has increased as a result of this problem, and various commodities are transported by road. Of course, there are other ways to carry people and commodities, including water and air. However, the rail transportation system is arguably the most effective and least expensive method of transporting numerous goods. But how are Iran's railroads doing?

To sum up the state of Iran's railways, we must conclude that while not ideal, circumstances are being improved. By offering rail transportation services, many businesses have simplified the situation for their clients. Most of these businesses excel at receiving, sending, and delivering cargo. When compared to other modes of transportation, the rail transit system is less dangerous. The implementation of this method will also lessen urban traffic, pollution, and accidents. It's important to note that most accidents involving freight and passenger trains included collisions with automobiles. Aside from all of these instances, I should point out that one of the best advantages of the train transportation technique is its ability to transfer a sizable amount of freight. In this research, we tried to survey Iran's high-speed railway situation and also briefly discusses railway way accidents and their root cause in Iran.

Keywords: vehicle, rail transportation system, Iran's railways, accidents.

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1. Introduction

One of the major problems is the railway accident, whose causes can be effectively understood to improve safety and decrease both financial and human losses in rail transit. It can be argued that safe cargo and passenger transportation is of utmost importance to managers of rail transportation, and the use of safe transportation methods necessitates a thorough comprehension of the factors that result in unsafe conditions, which can be attained by learning from previous experiences.

One of Iran's railroads' most crucial divisions, the General Department of Safety and Network Monitoring is in charge of and supervises any actions that could jeopardize train safety. One of the key objectives of the railroad sector is the prevention of rail accidents. One of the most crucial responsibilities of this general department is to gather, categorize, and analyze the data on accidents and occurrences to assess and implement the required precautions to prevent accidents. (سوانح در راه آهن کشور انواع و علل تحلیل آماری, n.d.)

The high efficiency of this sector of the economy is crucial since, on the one hand, it necessitates significant infrastructure investment and, on the other hand, because of the bottom line, it is one of the key pillars of economic growth and development of any society. Low fuel costs, little pollution of the environment, and great safety make the necessary investments justifiable.

The principle of scarcity and the best distribution of resources is a topic that has always interested people; limitation and scarcity are extremely evident in all areas, such as production factors, which lead to goods and services, so people construct conditions to make this happen. To access greater production and higher quality, and what satisfies this desire, it is better for life, and there is no other option than to use the facilities that are now available as best as possible; Boost performance (سیستماتیک مرور سوانح ریلی: مطالعات و تحلیل آماری تجزیه و بررسی, n.d.). The absence of adequate safety is one of the most significant flaws in transportation networks, particularly railways, which drives up costs and wastes excessive resources. One of the fundamental conditions for the growth of the rail transportation sector is the maintenance and improvement of the safety level. A thorough awareness of the shortcomings and issues in the rail network is necessary for the creation of safety measures. The Islamic Republic of Iran's railway system is also not an exception to this rule. There is a need for a suitable tool to analyze these data to identify the status of accidents and the relationships among their characteristics. As a result, by adopting appropriate safety measures, more train traffic will be guaranteed. The Islamic Republic of Iran's railways produces a lot of information, especially in safety systems like the accident registration system. To prevent or reduce the frequency of Iranian railroad accidents and ensure the safety of train traffic, the data linked to these incidents will be analyzed in this study. In the literature, there are studies where the authors have identified the features of rail accidents that are related to human variables associated with accidents, based on the research undertaken by the writers of this article in the field of data analysis related to rail accidents. To do this, the correlation analysis method is employed to ascertain if a given accident was caused by a human factor or a non-human component. (Yu et al., 2008)

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Errors will occur as long as human performance occurs in a complicated context, and their likelihood rises under stressful, overworked, and exhausting circumstances. Organizations must effectively manage errors to lower the likelihood of errors and their impacts. We will need management in all rails sub-sectors, including safety, fleet and line operation, budget allocation, training and employment of expert employees, and maintenance of lines, buildings, and fleet, to meet the growing demand for the use of this mode of transportation.

The causes of an accident can generally be divided into the following categories: catastrophes and natural events, vandalism and demolition activities, the presence of defects and defects in the line and rail vehicle components, negligence, neglect of related human resources, lack of understanding and culture of safety, and system limitations. In this regard, safety in rail transportation is achieved through the use of qualified and trained specialists, appropriate technology, and the application of rules and regulations related to the design, implementation, maintenance, and repair of the line, their components, and other similar items related to rail vehicles and their proper operation.

Additionally, according to accident data and records, the human mistake has always been the root cause of more than half of railway accidents, and this percentage will increase if the indirect contribution of human factors is taken into account. Wagons and line operators are in the following ranks. One of the most crucial topics that are discussed and looked at is understanding the variables and elements that contribute to neglect and human error. Training, discipline, suitable motivation and encouragement, adequate workplace amenities, ongoing medical checks, and other factors are some of the ways to lessen employee neglect and mistakes that occur frequently. (Yu et al., 2008) In this research, the influencing factors in rail accidents are discussed.

2. Methodology

The original and crucial list of keywords was chosen to offer a suitable and pertinent perspective to address the research questions after a thorough examination process in the accessible sources on the subject of Iran's Railway, Specifications, and a quick summary of recent rail-based catastrophes.

The terms "railways," "Iran's railway system," "rail-based accidents," and "characteristics of high-speed Iranian trains" were chosen to fully encompass the research literature.

Finally, a few sources on practical measures were founded and they were divided into three main areas.

1. Iran's high-speed rail transportation system.
2. Specification of the rail-based system in the territory.
3. High-speed rail transportation accidents.

This conceptual descriptive paper is based on a cross-sectional study reviewed by sources about the above-mentioned topics. The critical literature review was conducted in 5 main steps: (I) online database search based on keywords, (ii) first refinement based on selection criteria including title, abstract, and keywords of that paper, (iii) further refinement based on unique characteristics such as publishing year, language, type of document, type of access, region and country, etc., (iv) third refinement on abstract screening to consider focusing on the main topic,

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and (v) the last step is full-text review. Figure 1 shows the methodology of selecting resources to make a literature review of the mitigation carbon footprint in seaports.

Figure 1: Methodology

3. Introducing Iran's High-Speed Rail Transportation System

The country's rail transportation system currently contains 10,459 km of railway lines that were constructed between 1295 and now, according to the most recent government figures. About 22,735 daily wagons are moving through the country's freight system. The 583 locomotives that move these many wagons. These locomotives cover 124,000 kilometers daily on average. (پنج نکته شگفت انگیز در مورد قطارهای سریع السیر ایران- قاصدک 24, n.d.)

Iran's rail transportation system needs to be acknowledged as one of the best in the globe given that our nation is situated in one of the best transit hubs on the whole planet. However, this is regrettably not the case, and the main cause of this problem is the adoption of bad policies when creating the rail transportation system, particularly in the field of carrying commodities. Iran's railways are currently in worse than-ideal conditions as a result of this. The majority of the wagons in Iran's transportation system are worn out, there aren't any wagon facilities, the inspections aren't done properly, and the electronic bill of lading system isn't working. It accounts for 13% of the total. (وضعیت راه آهن ایران _ بررسی شرایط سیستم حمل و نقل ریلی کشور _ شرکت نمایندگی, n.d.)

Figure 2 displays the most recent railroad maps of Iran's interior with the following details:

1. The highest altitude is 2550 meters above sea level in FARS province.
2. The min altitude is sea level in the Caspian Sea area.
3. The longest tunnel is 3000 meters in HORMOZGAN province.
4. The longest bridge has 1430 meters in the GILAN province in the north of the country.
5. And the total rail transport was 14078 km in 2021.

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destination as you move. The self-propelled system is one in which each car has a separate drive motor that moves that car independently from the train in addition to being pushed by a locomotive and a moving engine in front of the train. As a result, this train travels more quickly than other trains in the nation. 2. The term "express train" differs depending on where you are in the world. For instance, in America, a high-speed train is any train that travels at a speed of more than 145 km/h. In opposition to this, the high-speed rail in Germany travels at a speed of 450 km/h. Normal Iranian trains cannot travel faster than 120 km/h, however, occasionally there are special trains, like the GHADIR train, whose top speed can reach 140 km/h on specific routes. The only high-speed train in Iran that travels at a speed of 160 to 180 kilometers per hour is the PARDIS train; the GHADIR train is not regarded as a high-speed train.

3. A lot of travelers believe that the PARDIS train only runs between Tehran and Mashhad. This mindset results from the fact that the majority of travelers who haven't purchased a bus or plane ticket to get to Mashhad opt to take the PARDIS bus train instead. Because it travels between Tehran and Mashhad in under 8 hours, drastically reducing their journey time. Given that the PARDIS bus train is also in operation on other lines, including Tehran-Qom-Tehran and Tehran-Yazd-Tehran, it is not necessarily terrible to know that this is a mistake.

4. The PARDIS train provides its passengers with several amenities, but one of the most amazing is the usage of seats that are just as comfy as those on an airplane. Given that so many VIP buses now employ this style of the seat in their cabins, some passengers understandably think that this form of seat is not considered a special railway feature. Therefore, by purchasing a VIP bus ticket, customers can simply enjoy the convenience of flying in a separate vehicle while sitting in airplane seats. The PARDIS train is a 4-star train that offers its passengers a variety of amenities, as we've already mentioned. But this is not a luxurious train. Because FADAK uses 5-star trains to transport people, or because RAJA has a train called Life in its rail fleet that is regarded as a fully functional train in every aspect. Even yet, it's good to know that the campus has just as many amenities as other first-class trains. Because by purchasing campus train tickets, travelers may easily enjoy riding by train that is outfitted with audio and video systems, cooling and heating systems, and wheelchairs for disabled passengers. Naturally, this kind of train is also impervious to noise, dust, and dampness, making it more comfortable to ride on.

3.1. Accidents in High-Speed Iran's Rail Transportation System

The rail system in Iran categorizes accidents into two groups: those that involve trains and those that don't. Railway mishaps include derailment incidents, rail car crashes, fires, train and wagon escapes, and other occurrences (mountain collapses, etc.). Placed. While non-railroad accidents are defined as collisions with automobiles at a level junction, accidents involving bystanders, passengers who fall from trains, stone-throwing incidents, etc. (Movahedi et al., 2007)

The causes of derailment accidents will be covered in the sections that follow, taking into account the high frequency of rail accidents.

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3.2. Factors Causing High-Speed Rail Accidents

The General Department of Traffic Protection and Safety divides the variables that contribute to high-speed rail accidents into categories such as those connected to human power, the line, locomotives and wagons, signs, etc. (سوانح ریلی: مطالعات و تحلیل آماری تجزیه و بررسی) (Railway Track Engineering - J. S. Mundrey - Google Libros, n.d.)

In the following, we discuss the factors that lead to rail accidents:

A. Lack of degaussing, moving before the needle is locked, choosing the incorrect path, moving before taking the path, the presence of a foreign object in the line or the needle, failing to restrain stopped wagons, hitting a wagon, improper loading, and improper curbing of wagons are examples of factors that contribute to human resource exploitation and error. The speed will be unlawful if the needle is inserted incorrectly. One can think of unlawful speed, exceeding the allowable speed, very low speed, and accidents brought on by changes in acceleration (rapid increase in speed/time at the termination point) as examples of speed that may result in rail accidents. The range of speed reduction (speed reduction zone) or its rapid increase in typical driving conditions (uphill and downhill) deviating from the lane due to acceleration changes (rapid speed reduction/time) at the beginning of the range of speed reduction (speed reduction zone) or its rapid decrease in typical driving conditions (slope-Faraz) pointed out.

B. Line reasons include issues with the line itself, line drooping, line twisting, component failure, shortage, and inappropriately high profile, as well as line escape, infrastructure failure, failure in the arc, and other issues—the majority of which are brought on by the aging of the lines.

C. Rail cars can malfunction for a variety of reasons, including poor braking, axle failure, a cut axle head, cushion adhesion, chassis fracture, collar loosening, etc.

D. Natural indicators and events, such as the existence of incorrect signals when entering and leaving the station, floods, earthquakes, landslides, storms, mountain falls, and line obstructions, among others, can be cited about the mechanism of leaving the line and the theories in this field. ((PDF) Assessing Railway Vehicle Derailment Potential Using Neural Networks, n.d.)

3.3. Factors Affecting the Creation of Human Error and Exploitation

The selection of variables for model creation will be aided by knowledge of the factors influencing human mistakes and exploitation. According to accident statistics, a sizable portion of the nation's high-speed rail accidents is attributable to human error issues. (Ciani et al., 2022) Numerous factors, including those related to the physical and biological, psychological and behavioral, economic, environmental, health and recreational facilities and services, and the cultural-educational factor, all have an impact on human errors, which rank as the nation's leading cause of railroad accidents. These situations are in various dimensions, and they directly or indirectly affect the likelihood of accidents. (Chinese Academy of Railway Sciences (CARS) - Railway Research (Developed by UIC), n.d.)

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Several police and employees involved in movement and safety might make mistakes and cause human error, including (locomotive drivers, etc.).

Additionally, it occasionally affects tourists and low-income citizens. Examples of mistakes made by agents and staff include using improper or partially open needles, failing to pay attention to signs, exceeding the allowed speed, using locomotives that are unfamiliar with the track, using inaccurate brake control, and granting permits.

He emphasized the disregard for loading guidelines, the failure of human resources to make prompt decisions, the imprecision of train inspections, etc. Additionally, incidents like careless pedestrians boarding trains, stone-throwing passengers and officials, youngsters playing on the tracks, etc. are included in the category of passenger and bystander errors. (Ciani et al., 2022)

The involvement of the important elements in an accident, such as experience, age, education level, etc., can be explored based on a broad assessment of accident statistics and the significance of the cases stated. The ability of individuals to perform tasks correctly is determined by their age. As we age, our physical and mental abilities decline, and our capacity to respond quickly to accidents sharply declines. (da Fonseca-Soares et al., 2022) On the other hand, a person's level of resistance to difficult working conditions declines, their perception of exhaustion rises, and their likelihood of having an accident also rises. On the other hand, as experience increases, so do information and context, which lowers the likelihood of an accident. The results of the research shows that most locomotive drivers have experienced accidents at the start of their careers (ranging in age from 25 to 81), which is attributable to a lack of training due to the delicate nature of the work and the impact of psychological variables on Young people's living conditions are taken into consideration, but as one's education level rises, one's perspective on working conditions broadens and deepens, and the likelihood of errors and accidents decreases. (Application of Artificial Intelligence Approach in the Analyses of Train Derailment Accidents | Request PDF, n.d.; da Fonseca-Soares et al., 2022).

3.4. Points of Speed Reduction / Normal Points of Travel and Their Relationship with Human Error

Reducing the speed entails going along the route at a reduced speed overall and at certain points along the way. This problem may be related to variables like infrastructure, pavement, fleet, and natural phenomena, among others. Accident research has revealed that certain incidents are linked to sites where there are speed restrictions, which are more visible in high-speed trains. Speed reduction zones are thought of as the weak parts of the route, and human mistakes in breaking traffic regulations may result in an accident. Using trained locomotive drivers and using warning devices will lessen accidents in this aspect. (Application of Artificial Intelligence Approach in the Analyses of Train Derailment Accidents | Request PDF, n.d.; Yu et al., 2008) In addition, the locomotive driver's negligence, lack of vigilance, carelessness, forgetfulness, failure to issue a caution order, tearing off or falling off the speed signs, etc. are among the situations that fail to observe the permitted speed in the normal running area as well as in the points of speed reduction. (سوانح در راه آهن کشور انواع و علل تحلیل آماری, n.d.)

4. conclusion

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The report claims that Iran's high-speed train status is unsatisfactory and that it must meet all requests because of the 85 million people who call the country home.

Furthermore, As previously said, this study aimed to explore and statistically review the studies of rail accidents. The investigation of the causes of rail faults will have a variety of factors, which may be inferred from the results. Based on the results of this survey, it was discovered that no nationwide studies had been done in which the criticality of occupations was examined from the perspective of rail faults. Because of this, studies on human errors have primarily focused on control room operators, particularly in the industries of oil, gas, and petrochemicals. In this regard, it is advised to research the role of rail errors in the accidents of the aforementioned sectors given the significance and prevalence of road, rail, and aviation accidents in the nation. Additionally, it is recommended that more research be done to determine how training, experience, stress, job organization, human-machine interaction, and other shaping elements affect the likelihood of rail errors. The findings of this analysis also demonstrated that the majority of studies are restricted to the detection and assessment of rail faults as well as the function of management and engineering controls in lowering the severity and likelihood of rail faults.

One of the other recommendations made in this study is to look into the effects of enhancing the safety culture and devising and putting into practice the idea of poka-yoke (infallibility).

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